

A New Extractive Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of *p*-Nitroaniline

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On the basis of diazotization reaction a new sensitive extractive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of *p*-nitroaniline. *p*-Nitroaniline is diazotized with nitrite in hydrochloric acid medium and subsequently coupled with α -naphthol to give a purple coloured azo dye in alkaline medium. (λ_{\max} 580 nm, ϵ_{\max} 3.7×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The azo dye formed is extractable in iso-amyl alcohol, giving a blue coloured extract having molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of 5.2×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹, $0.0026 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively at λ_{\max} 610 nm. Several common species, viz, inorganic cations, phenols, nitrocompounds, aldehydes, ketones, etc. present in polluted water do not interfere. Primary aromatic amines interfere when present in high concentration.

p-NITROANILINE, a well known toxic compound, is widely used in the synthesis of dyes and other intermediates¹. It is regarded as a potential carcinogen in presence of nitrite². It also causes liver damage on prolonged exposure and has the strong ability to form methemoglobin in man. This is due to the fact that enzyme systems catalyse oxidation of the amino group and reduction of the nitro group to known cyanopathic nitroso and hydroxylamine derivatives which hinder oxygen transport to tissue by forming Hb-complex³. The degree of toxicity in *p*-nitroaniline is high due to the presence of substituted amino group along with the nitro group in aromatic ring.

Very few methods have been reported⁴⁻⁶ for the detection and determination of *p*-nitroaniline but these lack sensitivity and selectivity. In the present investigation a method has been developed for the determination of *p*-nitroaniline which is based on the diazotization of *p*-nitroaniline with nitrite in hydrochloric acid medium and subsequent coupling of the resulting *p*-nitrophenyl diazonium ion with α -naphthol in alkaline medium⁷. The azo dye formed is extracted in iso-amyl alcohol. The blue coloured iso-amyl alcohol extract of the azo dye shows maximum absorption at 610 nm having molar absorptivity of 5.2×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and Sandell's sensitivity of $0.0026 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. By the present method as low as 0.1 ppm *p*-nitroaniline can be determined. The method is very simple, selective and the dye formed is far more stable.

Experimental

Apparatus: An ECIL spectrophotometer model GS 865 and Carl-Zeiss Spekol with 1 cm matched glass cells were used for spectral measurements.

pH measurements were made with Systronics pH meter, model 322.

Reagents:

***p*-Nitroaniline solution:** A stock solution of 1 mg/ml *p*-nitroaniline was prepared in 20% aqueous ethanol. A working solution containing 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ *p*-nitroaniline was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock with deaerated double distilled water. The commercially available reagent was crystallised twice before use.

NO_2^- Solution: A 1×10^{-3} M solution of nitrite was prepared in deaerated double distilled water from predried (about 4 hr at 110°) AnalaR grade sodium nitrite.

α -Naphthol: 0.2% w/v solution was prepared in 20% aqueous ethanol. The reagent was crystallised twice before use.

Sodium hydroxide: 2 N aqueous solution was prepared in glass distilled water.

EDTA: 10% w/v aqueous solution of disodium salt of EDTA was prepared.

Solution of interfering ions: These were prepared from AnalaR grade chemicals.

Procedure: An aliquot containing 5-20 μg of *p*-nitroaniline was taken in a 125 ml pear shaped separatory funnel and diluted to ~ 50 ml with distilled water. 1 ml of nitrite solution was added to this. The acidity of the solution was adjusted to ~ 0.5 M hydrochloric acid and the solution was allowed to stand for 5 min with occasional shaking. 1 ml of EDTA (for masking ions) and 2 ml of α -naphthol solutions were added and the mixture was shaken for another 1 min. Excess of NaOH solution was added to make the solution alkaline and the purple coloured dye formed was

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extracted in two, 5 ml portions of iso-amyl alcohol. The blue coloured iso-amyl alcohol extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured at 610 nm. The concentration of *p*-nitroaniline was computed from a calibration curve prepared in similar manner. A reagent blank extracted in iso-amyl alcohol was taken as reference for absorbance measurements. Samples with higher concentration were diluted appropriately prior to determination.

Results and Discussion

All spectral studies were made with 50 ml of distilled water containing required amount of *p*-nitroaniline. The absorption spectra of the azo dye in aqueous as well as in iso-amyl alcohol is shown in Fig. 1, which shows the maximum absorption in aqueous medium at 580 nm while in iso-amyl alcohol medium it is at 610 nm. The absorption of the reagent blank was found to be negligible in this region.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of azo dye in iso-amylalcohol and water. concentration of *p*-nitroaniline—12 $\mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml}$. Curve A—iso amylalcohol and curve B—water.

Effect of variables : It was observed that at least 0.2 *M* hydrochloric acid was necessary for complete diazotization and no change in absorbance was observed upto 1 *M* HCl. *p*-Nitrophenyl-diazonium chloride formed was found to be stable for 60 min and the minimum time for coupling reaction was found to be 2 min. The azo dye was stable upto 30 hr.

At least 1 : 1 mole ratio of *p*-nitroaniline and nitrite was necessary for full colour development and constant absorbance values were obtained upto 20 molar excess. It was found that 20 molar excess of α -naphthol was necessary for full colour development and no change in absorbance was observed even if large excess of α -naphthol was added.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, sensitivity and reproducibility : The colour system was found to obey Beer's law in the range of 5-20 μg *p*-nitroaniline per 10 ml iso-amyl alcohol extract, extracted from 50 ml aliquot of sample at 610 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $5.2 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0026 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively, as calculated from Beer's law data.

In the water system, the molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.7 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0037 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 580 nm, respectively. The reproducibility of the method was checked by replicate analysis of standard *p*-nitroaniline solution and the results showed the method to be fairly reproducible.

Effect of foreign species : The effect of foreign species commonly present in polluted water were studied by adding known amount of ions to the sample solution and determining *p*-nitroaniline by the recommended procedure. Metal ions forming hydroxide in alkaline medium are expected to interfere. However a large number of these ions were masked with EDTA. Bi(II) and Fe(III) were masked with tartrate. Fe(II) and Cr(VI) interfere. Tolerance limits shown in Table 1 are the amount of foreign species that cause $\leq 2\%$ error in the determination of *p*-nitroaniline.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE SPECIES
Concentration of *p*-nitroaniline=0.25 ppm

Species (Tolerance limit in ppm)			
Li ⁺ (100)	Be ⁺⁺ (100)	Mg ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Ca ⁺⁺ (100) ^a
Sr ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Ba ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Zr ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Cr ⁺⁺ (10)
Mo ⁺⁺ (100)	W ⁺⁺ (100)	Fe ⁺⁺ (50) ^b	Co ⁺⁺ (100) ^a
Ni ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Cu ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Zn ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Ca ⁺⁺ (100) ^a
Hg ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Pb ⁺⁺ (100) ^a	Sb ⁺⁺ (100)	Bi ⁺⁺ (100) ^b
Se ⁺⁺ (100)	Te ⁺⁺ (100)	B ⁺⁺ (100)	F ⁻ (100)
Br ⁻ (100)	I ⁻ (25)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (800)	NO ₃ ⁻ (200)
PO ₄ ³⁻ (200)	SO ₃ ²⁻ (50) ^c	SiO ₃ ²⁻ (100)	Phenol (25)
	HCHO (25)		

a=Masked with EDTA ; 1 ml of 10% aqueous solution of disodium salt.

b=Masked with tartrate ; 1 ml of 10% aqueous solution of sod. pot. tartrate.

c=Masked with H₂O₂ ; 0.1 ml of 1% H₂O₂ of 20 volume solution.

Effect of some primary amines were studied. 5 to 6 fold excess of *o*-, *p*-toluidine, benzidine, *o*-, *m*-nitroaniline and aniline do not interfere with the method as these compounds are having different λ_{max} with α -naphthol in alkaline medium (Table 2). Interference of higher concentration of benzidine can be eliminated by precipitating

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DIFFERENT AZO DYES IN ISO-AMYL ALCOHOL USING α -NAPHTHOL

Sl. No.	Amine tested	λ_{max} nm
1.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	490
2.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	450
3.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	420
4.	Aniline	505
5.	Benzidine	530
6.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	610
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	490
8.	α -Naphthylamine	520
9.	β -Amino, α -naphthol	—
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	525
11.	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol*	620
12.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenol*	630

*Interferes with the method.

benzidine with sulfuric acid before diazotization of the sample.

Effect of extraction with higher alcohol : *n*-Butanol, *n*-pentanol, *n*-hexanol and *n*-octanol were tried for the extraction of the azo dye. With butanol, the separation of the two layers was found difficult. *n*-Pentanol, iso-pentanol and *n*-hexanol was found satisfactory for extraction. *n*-Octanol reduced the sensitivity of the method. Iso-amyl alcohol was found to be the best amongst the alcohols tried. Extraction procedure increased the sensitivity several times.

Comparison with other methods : The methods reported³⁻⁵ for the detection and determination of *p*-nitroaniline are not highly sensitive and some of the methods suffer from the interferences of other primary aromatic amines, as all of these primary amines have been reported to have maximum absorption at the same wavelengths. The present method is rapid, reproducible, sensitive and free from the interference of large group of foreign species. Independence of the colour-intensity from *pH*, temperature and reagent concentration are the added advantages of the method. The method is satisfactory for the determination of *p*-nitroaniline in water samples.

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